

I've Been Emotionally Violated. What do I do?

COLLEEN FLETCHER

I also call this mind raping ... and it is as ugly as it sounds.

First off, let me tell you this, I AM SO SORRY. So, you've just had a distressing experience with an energy healer or Reiki practitioner or hypnotherapist (from here on out I will refer to this as 'therapist').

This is an unfortunate experience that can occur after one receives energy healing/Reiki, metaphysical guidance, or hypnotherapy. I've had it happen to me as I've had people in my own family do such things. Often times violations like this occur from parents. I have had friends ask how I can help after it has happened to them, and I have helped to heal clients after these negative experiences have occurred and affected their lives.

It starts like this ...

You have heard that energy healing/Reiki or hypnotherapy can do wonders for your whole being. Things like, healing damaged cells, fixing daily damage caused by stress and negative surroundings, depression, feelings of fatigue or anxiety, and sickness. And, being that it is very effective in purifying and releasing old traumas and emotions you think, "hey, this sounds like something safe and nurturing for me to do." You look online, or maybe even in a phone book (gasp) and find someone listed as a therapist that sounds good to you. (You don't really know what you're looking for anyway, right?) You book your appointment and wait for your scheduled day to arrive.

It's time for your appointment - I certainly hope that you have been asked to fill out some sort of health history and been guided as to how to prepare for your appointment.

All goes well, until you notice an uneasy feeling in your belly, or maybe a headache starts during your session. You don't know if it is appropriate to mention these feelings now (most people don't) so you just carry on. *And, YES, it is appropriate to mention these feelings*

as they come up. Maybe you feel OK after your appointment and your feelings of unease come on later?? It does vary for each person, and often it is a cumulative feeling. As everyone is different in how they experience energy work or hypnotherapy, both good and bad, you might have your own unique feelings. Honor those, and trust in yourself.

My own experiences with emotional violations started when I was very young. I had no idea how to take care of myself emotionally so I (unknowingly) continually manifested ill health. It was a compounding effect that I had no idea was even happening.

For me, it was allergies, asthma, upset stomach, and continual colds. At about the age of 20 I started to hear that emotional violation was even a thing. (If you don't know something exists then how can you ask for help, right?) I knew I did not feel well, I was starting to realize that my thought processes made a difference in my overall health, so I kept plugging along in life.

As time went on, I knew my feelings were valid, I began to trust my own intuition even more, and I started seeing the effects this had on others. Most of all, I wanted to help others so they were not emotionally violated in the first place, and if they were, I wanted to help clear up the effects of it in their life so they could begin to thrive again. As I healed myself, I healed others.

Signs you have been emotionally violated:

- You are extremely tired after a session.
- You have an upset stomach.
- You are continually tired long after your session.
- You have, or get a headache or migraine, especially if you are not prone to them.
- You become filled with fear.
- You feel an unexplained dark presence around you.

- Your mind is unfocused which does not clear up within 24-48 hours.
- You finished your appointment knowing that ‘something is wrong.’
- Rest is not helping.
- You feel as though someone is watching you.
- You feel as though someone is looking through your eyes at your life.
- A feeling of being violated emotionally is within you.
- You begin to severely question exactly what happened.
- You have negative feeling after your session.
- You become depressed about the session.
- You get a feeling that you were taken advantage of.
- You begin to sense that you *allowed* this to happen.
- You did not listen to intuition, whatever the reason was.
- You felt as though you are/were a victim.
- The reason you went in in the first place is worse.

Now, some of these symptoms do happen after a session due to your body purging its self from long held toxins. These normal symptoms last for about 24-48 hours. A prime example of this is having diarrhea for a couple of days. You feel fine, your head is clear with feelings of vitality for yourself. You just have a bit of an extra cleanse happening with your body. Normal!

You can also feel changes within yourself for a few months after the session ... like positive ones. This is your body, mind and spirit merging all of the new positive experiences into your total well-being.

What to do after you notice this has happened?

First, I don't recommend another appointment with the same person.

Drink extra water. This helps to flush out any toxins from your body, thus helping to flush out further negative actions.

Know that you did nothing to deserve this.

Take a walk, a stroll or a run. The point is, move your body to help clear your brain.

Get out and explore nature. A park, a forest, even your own back yard. Sit for 5 minutes and reconnect. Maybe shed a few tears, but get up, dust off your backside and step into your new reality.

Meditate to reconnect with your inner peace.

Take a bath or shower. Sea salt is an amazing cleanser of such events. When you are finished with your bath or shower take a cold shower. This can be a super quick cold rinse, but it is super helpful.

This is the best personal space cleanser that I have used - ever! Well, apart from smudging, but smudging is not always an option. It is called Sacred Space. This is what I use in between clients. Many parents use this on their kids when they come home from school.

Often times a negative experience in life can be turned around into something more positive for you. Use this negative to learn, grow, and thrive further. I have faith in the amazing person that you are!

Positive effects of Metaphysical Guidance, Energy Healing ...

- Your skin looks more radiant.
- You find it easier to work.
- Stress has reduced in your life.
- You have less physical pain in your life.
- You smile more.
- Past emotional blockages have lifted.
- You are more confident.
- You have more energy.
- You have more vitality in life.
- You are happy.
- You trust in your decisions.
- Your sleep is more relaxed.
- You feel your personal boundaries are strengthening.
- You no longer feel like you are a victim.

How to find a therapist?

Many times, consumers don't know what to expect with various forms of body work, energy work, hypnotherapy, esthetics, and metaphysical guidance; this is designed to give you the confidence in trusting that the therapist you are going to see for your health is right for you. Keep in mind that you are building a relationship. That relationship is of vital importance. So, here is what I suggest doing to ensure you can recognize if your therapist is competent or beneficial in your life.

1) *How to tell if a therapist is competent or not?* Do they have credentials? Well, yes, credentials are important, and are a great guideline to ensure your therapist has training in the desired field.

a) Ask about where they went to school? When did they finish their training? Another thing you might ask them is if they enjoyed the school they went to, and why?

b) Ask to see their credentials. When you see their credentials check to see if they are current.

c) Talk with them before setting up your appointment – ask if you can come in and meet with them first. A good therapist will always say 'yes.'

d) Ask if they belong to any professional organizations.

e) And then, there is this ... the truth about credentials – sometimes the most highly qualified therapist is not right for you, so all of those fancy pieces of paper are worthless in your case.

You have to trust yourself. Many states in the U.S. don't require much in the way of training for energy healing. For this reason, I encourage you to talk with the person first. More than once, if needed. If they have minimal to no credentials, ask them why and see what their reasoning may be. They may have valid concerns/reasons for not having credentials.

I can go on and on about all of the wonderful services I offer and all of my credentials, however, the most important aspect of finding the right therapist is the relationship that the two of you have and will continue to have. You

need to feel safe and comfortable. It is my goal in life to help you feel safe and comfortable, I do know that not everyone will feel that way with me. And, I am so happy that you know and trust yourself well enough to acknowledge those feelings.

2) *Client confidentiality; your privacy, it matters.* Your personal health care is no one else's business. I will not talk to others about it, nor will I share any of your personal information. I do love glowing reports from you about my services, however, it is your choice if you share that information with others.

3) *What to expect (with me anyway).* Upon arrival you will fill out a client intake form, or you will have received it online. So please have that filled out and sent in before your appointment – please arrive 10 mins early to do this so that your session can start on time. After this is filled out, I will go through this info to further assist you in your total health.

4) *No one, (yes, that includes me) knows everything or has all of the answers.* Because of this, I encourage you to look at other therapists. I will guide you in what I offer to be the best fit for you and refer you to others if needed.

Just a bit more guidance and material to help you along the way in this powerful journey.

People come to me to relax and let go of their garbage, and it does end up in my space. Because of this, I am constantly cleaning out energies and vibes from my work space. The last thing I want is for you to take home someone else's garbage. I also don't want to take home that garbage. So, I cleanse it all out, all of the time. Many of my clients know where to send excess energy in my room as well.

Not all therapists/people who do energy work know they are harmful to you. Many don't do it on purpose, however some do. Think of a used car salesman; some are good, some are not. It is something for you to watch out for, as it is important to your whole health. Their lack of boundaries need not hurt you!

Following are some questions to help you further identify ways to encourage your whole health. These questions can also help when looking for a therapist.

Are you suffering from emotional pain, distress, anger, frustration, sadness, etc.?

Looking for a deeper connection with yourself, searching for self, feeling lost, invisible, unappreciated, unloved, feeling stuck?

Are you suffering from recurring physical pain? Low back pain, neck pain, tennis elbow, etc.?

Are you pregnant? Did you know massage therapy can shorten maternity hospital stays and can make for an easier labor?

Are you taking any medications? Are you wanting to stop taking so many medications?

Have you had any injuries? Have you had any car accidents or other physical/emotional trauma?

Do you have limited range of motion in your joints and muscles?

Are you wanting to improve your circulation? Are your hands and feet often cold?

Have you had any surgeries? Do you have any scar tissue? Do you have numbing or tingling in your fingers or toes?

Are you living with constant stress? Is your stress home or work related? Both?

Do you sleep 5-8 hours every night? Are your sleep patterns restless? Do you have recurring dreams or nightmares?

Do you wish to change a habit? Stop smoking, weight reduction, nail biting, etc.

Do you suffer from migraines?

Are you aware of the benefits of energy work, massage, metaphysics, skin care and hypnotherapy?

Are you experiencing dramatic life changes or shifts? Are you finding your values, patterns/routines, belief systems are being challenged or changing?

Do you find yourself searching for answers, knowledge, peace, happiness, grounding or spirituality?

Are you ready to take full responsibility for your life? Ready to change direction and invite new experiences into your life?

About Colleen Fletcher, L.M.T., L.E., C.Ht., Reiki Master, Ph.M.

With a life beginning in self-doubt, Colleen Fletcher has paved a path in personal growth for herself and her clients. Guiding others in living a life free of self-doubt in her private practice (established in 1995), she happily teaches you to live without pain, filled with confidence and purpose. Currently, living in Boise, Idaho, Colleen frequents some of the world's most stunning hot springs.

Metaphysical Healing – New Thought or Old?

J. JOY MAESTAS

Universal Light Ministries Tucson

We hear a lot about New Thought, and people use this term interchangeable with Metaphysical practices, being positive. But is it really NEW or are we just recycling thoughts and updating the terminology?

The Science of Mind magazine that was 1st published in 1927 by Ernest Holmes brought new thought into the main stream. I say this as instead of having to go to a meeting and being branded as having bazaar thoughts of creation and life. People were free to explore this information in the privacy of their home without judgment from anyone who saw them attending such an outlandish meeting.

In his book “The Science of Mind, in the chapter titled ANOTHER GREAT DISCOVERY—THOUGHT REACHED OTHERS it was stated, “he could think of them and heal them.” Many credit him with being “THE” New Thought teacher.

However, Mary Baker Eddy who registered the "Science and Health" program in 1875 was already teaching the Principle of scientific mental healing and that physical illness can be corrected by prayer in a positive atmosphere and that this information was something we had but lost with all the religious dogma through the ages. She gave all credit to the Divine Mind of God within us and not to our own power (paraphrased from “Science and Mind” with keys to the Scriptures by Mary Baker Eddy Chapter 6 Science, Theology, Medicine page 110 v.15-27 (The demonstration lost and found).

With this we have the basis of Metaphysical Healing and positive thought as currently taught by Dr. Paul Leon Masters in his course “Master’s Degree Course Study Modules vol. 2, The Practitioner’s Metaphysical Healing Practice. Meditating daily and connecting with your inner God Spirit should be the first step in awakening that healing within that helps you to be able to heal others. One thing they all stress is to heal yourself first. Take the beam out of your

own eye before you try to take the splinter out of your brother or sister.

Since we are electrical energy in our inherent nature, with metaphysics we learn to understand we have the ability to send this energy to others. This flow of energy that comes from the Divine into our body and out again, mirrors the eastern practice of Reiki.

Reiki is the eastern healing modality that teaches hands on healing method by sending your energy to someone by thought or hands on. The energy will then go to the area where the healing is most needed.

With Metaphysical healing treatments work much the same way, however the energy you are sending is made in a meditative state of oneness with the Universal God Mind, so the energy is not just your thought energy but the energy that is flowing from the Oneness Source through you to the other individual seeking healing. Again, this can be done long distance or in person. Where Reiki can be hands on Metaphysical methods can be more of holding your hands above the body and not touching it combined with meditation and affirmations.

So how old is this teaching of healing with the Universal Mind Energy? Much before 1875 When Mary Baker Eddy set down the exact steps of being one with the God within to heal. Jesus would meditate alone daily or pray and then he went and healed, but the practice goes way back before him. All religions on earth have some form of energy healing that is done and was passed down from the Angelic Messenger to Shaman to student.

Metaphysics or New Thought is not new. We are being now made aware of the collective energy that has always been there, but we were too concerned with other things to want to connect with our Divine energy, our Spirit Guides, our Angelic Guides who come straight from the center of our creator. They bring peace, knowledge and yes prosperity. How can we

spread the good news that God is within and we create our own heaven on earth unless we have the means to do so?

All through the ages we have been being guided towards this time in our collective history. We are calling it New Thought, but it's been around since the beginning of time.

When the Pagans celebrated the first Summer solstice, they were giving thanks for being one with nature and using Nature to heal. When the Christians started celebrating Easter they were giving thanks for renewal and rebirth. During this time the Hindus were celebrating *Holi* or *Phagwah* a popular spring festival. Holi commemorates the slaying of the demoness Holika by Lord Vishnu's devotee Prahlad. Out with the bad, in with the good. You will find spring time celebrations in all religions and most relate to being healed and given a new body. We are all one and we all celebrate the good.

It's not new it's always been there, waiting for us to catch up, wake up and become aware that you are in charge of this earthly experiment. What you think and say has a direct reaction on your life and those around you. The information has always been in you, now turn the page and read what you already know as truth. Be kind to one another and help one another. Think positive in all things and all things positive will come to you. This is the law of attraction, the universal law of love, the golden rule.

We may call it New Thought and I look at it this way. The light bulb came on and it seems like a new thought to us, but we have known about it for a very long time. It was just buried very deep with us. Now we have the time to actually ask the question of how this can be done and receive the answers that are already here. New Thought? No, not really. Forgotten Thought would be more like it. We who study the Way of The Magi want to help the world remember the oneness that was forgotten.

About Joy Maestas

J. Joy Maestas, known as Rev. Joy, is an ordained metaphysical minister with the International Metaphysical Ministry. She received her Master of Metaphysical Science from the University of Metaphysics in Sedona, Arizona. She is currently working toward her Doctorate. Rev. Joy founded Universal Light Ministries in Tucson to help others live positively and find the Universal Divine Love within themselves and has written numerous books on metaphysics.